

As Moore's law slows down yet the need to accelerate computation continues, scientists are shifting their focus to new hardware and architectures.

New and emerging computing paradigms and technologies

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It has been said many times already: we are nearing the end of exponential scaling (also known as Moore's law) that those of us in the computing industry have been used to – or perhaps rather addicted to – for decades. Because just as with an addiction, it can be very hard to sober up. Fortunately, nature does not enforce “cold turkey” on the chips industry. It started giving clear warning signals when Dennard scaling ended around 2004-2007 [18]. The cost of transistors started rising when the 28 nm technology node was introduced around 2015: a transistor at 7 nm is now 17% more expensive than its 28 nm counterpart. We had been used to transistor costs dropping, but since chip fabrication technology has become increasingly expensive, the cost has been rising noticeably [19]. Although researchers and chip manufacturers are still able to come up with clever techniques to keep Moore's law going for some years to come, we will “run out of money before we run out of physics”, as Dan Reed, former vice president at Microsoft said not too long ago in 2016 [20].

It is therefore not surprising that the computing industry is looking for ways other than Moore's law to keep the speed of computations up. One way forward appears to be to tailor the hardware to the computational problems at hand, instead of building faster universal machines based on the von Neumann architecture which tackle all computational tasks with one architecture. It is important to keep in mind that these new hardware techniques are being developed to add to, rather than replace, this architecture which has been successfully in use for over 75 years.

It is not only speed that has increased sharply: in recent years: particularly in the last few years, the cost of energy has risen considerably. It was initially caused by the economy's surprisingly fast recovery from the downturn caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. Even more recently, the war in Ukraine has made the energy market unpredictable, and this has increased pressure for computer system architecture to be as energy efficient as possible. Again, one way to accomplish this is to tune the architecture to the specific task, rather than developing one architecture that handles all the tasks.

In this section of the HiPEAC Vision, “The race for new hardware” we focus on several hardware approaches that on the one hand tackle a specific class of computational problems, and on the other hand promise to make central processing units run faster. In this introductory chapter, we briefly introduce these techniques to help readers better understand the remaining chapters.

There are many new computing paradigms but, for the sake of space, we will focus on those that we think are currently the furthest developed and/or the most promising.

Key insights

- Although Moore's law appears to continue, it is evidently slowing down.
- Improving device speed is not the only way to improve the speed of computations: architectures tuned to solving specific problems will be successfully leveraged to accelerate computations.
- Quantum computing makes it possible to solve specific problems that are practically unsolvable using classical (von Neumann) computers.
- New architectures modelled on biological neural networks promise to reduce energy consumption for solving specific problems.
- Materials research is key to developing new and innovative computing devices. Current examples include research to develop practical quantum devices, and to develop new memory and (analogue) computing devices.
- Introducing new computing paradigms requires the development of new programming models in addition to those based on the von Neumann architecture.
- The development of quantum computing has given a boost to information and complexity theory. These fields will grow in importance as new paradigms develop, evolving from pure theoretical into a combined theoretical/experimental discipline.
- Several architectural challenges lie ahead, in both the development of architectures for new devices and in embedding these devices into existing ones.
- Integrated circuit (IC) fabrication processes require large amounts of energy and fresh water, and due to their toxic waste can put high pressure on the environment.

Key recommendations

- Establish and stimulate centres of competence that combine the strength of Europe’s position in the fundamental fields of computing (information theory, complexity theory, computer architecture, algorithm design, programming paradigms) with European industrial initiatives. This will both attract top talent and develop a strong European industrial presence in the field of new computing devices.
- Strive to restore Europe’s leading role in new technologies and paradigms, as it did some decades ago with the establishment of emerging device research in the International Technology Roadmap for Semiconductors (ITRS).
- Put emphasis on development that interlinks research to innovative, practical applications.
- Invest in designing and fabricating novel IC technologies for very high-volume applications that have a significantly lower environmental impact, and at the same time apply the lessons learned from those new fabrication processes to existing ones.

Introducing quantum computing

Quantum computing is a radically new way to consider information processing based on the unique properties of quantum physics: superposition and entanglement of states. The idea first proposed by Richard Feynman in 1982 would allow the solving of problems that are far too complex to be tackled by current computers. Since then, progress in physics and technology has gradually transformed what used to be considered a dream into a reality. Although we are still far from being able to design and fabricate an operational quantum computer, it is now becoming a very concrete possibility.

Research and development activities at both academic and industrial levels are now engaged in a race towards quantum computing. It is a race of multiple dimensions: a race among a number of candidate qubit technologies, a race for architecture and hardware options, a race for software and programming, a race between nations and a race to attract and retain the best talent.

Read more in the HiPEAC Vision article “The race towards operational quantum computers”.

Neuromorphic computing

Our reflections on neuromorphic computing are based on “A Survey of Neuromorphic Computing and Neural Networks in Hardware” by Catherine Schuman et al [21], and the “2022 Roadmap on Neuromorphic Computing and Engineering” by Dennis V. Christensen et al [22].

When we compare the von Neumann architecture to the human brain, we notice differences not only in organizational structure, but also in processing capabilities and power requirements. One thing that stands out is the way data is moved in the von Neumann architecture: processing and data storage are separated, requiring data to be moved from memory to the processor for processing, and then moved back again to memory for storage. The bandwidth of the channel between memory and processor is one of the determining factors in the overall performance of the system. Another notable difference is the intrinsic capability of the human brain to learn, which is lacking in von Neumann-based computer architectures. Not unexpectedly, researchers have therefore turned to biological systems for inspiration for new approaches to data processing. One field that sprang from this is neuromorphic computing, which takes its inspiration from the structure of biological neural networks.

The term neuromorphic computing was coined by Carver Mead in 1990. Mead was referring to very large-scale integration (VLSI) designs consisting of analogue components that were more or less a copy of biological neural systems. Nowadays it means biologically *inspired* neural networks, implemented using either analogue or digital circuits. These networks are notable for being highly connected and parallel, co-locating computing and storage, and for their low energy consumption. Neuromorphic architectures can solve specific types of problems faster, using less chip real estate, and less power. More recently, two direc-

tions in neuromorphic computing have begun to emerge: spike-based processing systems and dedicated neural electronic architectures that form neuron and synaptic circuits, called artificial neural networks.

Operations are orchestrated by a clock in von Neumann architectures¹. Neuromorphic systems on the other hand are driven not only by time but also by data and events. That holds in particular for spike-based neural networks, while artificial neural networks are predominantly time-driven. A strong cross fertilization between these two prevailing architectures exists.

The field of neuromorphic computing is highly interdisciplinary. Disciplines such as materials research play an important role in the search for efficient implementations of neuromorphic circuits, both analogue and digital. Materials research is a key shared interest of the fields of neuromorphic computing and quantum computing. There are indeed more similarities between these research fields. Embedding new accelerator devices in existing von Neumann architectures requires careful architectural design to reap the benefits of combining them. To enable efficient programming of these embedded neuromorphic compute devices, new programming models need to be developed. What is more, although maybe less prominent than in quantum computing, neuromorphic networks have renewed interest in both complexity theory and algorithm design.

Intel and IBM have developed chips based on neuromorphic architectures:

¹ There are however some hardware architectures based on self-timed circuits that do not require a clock signal. Such architectures are not widely in use.

“loihi” in the case of Intel and “TrueNorth” at IBM. There is also a number of start-ups in the field: brainschip [23], GrAI Matter Labs [24], Innatera [25], iniLabs [26], INSTAR Robotics [27], Intrinsic Semiconductor Technologies [28], Koniku [29] and MemComputing [30].

Forecasts for the neuromorphic computing market vary from \$12 billion in 2027 to \$32 billion in 2035, rising from \$200 million in 2025, provided that fundamental technical issues can be solved. Even conservative market research forecasts a market worth at least \$8.6 billion. It would mean a growth in 2035 of close to two orders of magnitude in 10 years. [32,33,34]

In summary, neuromorphic computing is an interesting field with great technical potential, yet many technical challenges to be solved. It is a field that we think will play an increasingly important role in information processing in the years to come. We will revisit neuromorphic computing in future updates of the HiPEAC Vision.

Figure 1. Block diagram of the major memory blocks of Intel’s Loihi chip, where the various connectivities, configurations and dynamic states of all the neurons that are mapped to the neuromorphic core. Each core incorporates a total of 2 Mib (including ECC). From [31].

Figure 2. TrueNorth architecture. Panels are organized into rows at three different scales (core, chip, and multichip) and into columns at four different views (neuroscience inspiration, structural, functional, and physical). (A) The neurosynaptic core is loosely inspired by the idea of a canonical cortical microcircuit. (B) A network of neurosynaptic cores is inspired by the cortex’s two-dimensional sheet. (C) The multichip network is inspired by the long-range connections between cortical regions shown from the macaque brain. Merolla et al. [35]

Neuromorphic computing, neurons and synapses

Neuromorphic devices are modelled on biological neurons, made up of neural circuits.

Nervous tissue in almost all animals consists of electrically excitable cells, called neurons, that communicate with other neurons through synapses. Many interconnected neurons together form a neural network circuit. Typical neurons consist of a cell body, the soma, and two types of filaments that protrude from the soma: dendrites and an axon. Dendrites are strongly branched, and end very close to the soma, usually only a few micrometres away. The axon, on the other hand, can be very long, of the order of one metre, or sometimes even longer. Axons are less branched, and end in synapses. The dendrites serve as the receivers of signals, the axon functions as the transmitter. The end of an axon consists of a synapse, which transmits the signal to the dendrite of another neuron, but axon-axon synapses and dendrite-dendrite synapses are also found [43].

Neurons process information through electrical and chemical processes. Neurons are electrically excited when the voltage across their membrane changes and passes a particular threshold within a certain time interval. When that happens, an all-or-nothing pulse, called an action potential is sent down the axon, activating the synaptic connections of the axon. Depending on the synapse, some increase the net voltage that reaches the next neuron, others decrease the net voltage.

Neuromorphic computing devices mimic the neurons and the connections between neurons: the synapses. The soma, axons and dendrites are abstracted away, but not the interaction between neurons through synapses, which differentiate neuromorphic devices from classical digital circuits.

Several main streams can be distinguished in neuromorphic computing: in analogue neuromorphic devices, the characteristics of specific materials are exploited to simulate the behaviour of synapses and the reaction of neurons to the synaptic stimuli. In digital neuromorphic devices, this behaviour is implemented using digital circuits. Of course, there are also mixed analogue/digital neuromorphic systems. Several packages exist that exhibit the behaviour of neuromorphic systems implemented in software. [44]

Schematic illustration of neuromorphic system. a) Biological model: the biological neuron receives inputs from other neurons by interconnected synapses; b) Equivalent electronic model: the electronic neuron for accumulating inputs generated by different pre-neurons through resistive switching memristor (RS) synapses to implement the functions of spiking neural network [45].

Introducing spintronics

Spintronics is a marriage between electronics and magnetism that exploits the spin of electrons, in addition to their charge, to reveal new phenomena. These are then exploited in innovative components and circuits with improved performance, particularly in terms of power consumption, or offering new functions.

Until now, the main application of spintronics in computer design has been in the field of storage and memory. A number of technologies have been developed for the various needs of the computer memory hierarchy (Figure 3), technologies that are always seeking the “ideal” memory device: fast to read and write, providing high-densities, economically viable and non-volatile.

A new type of magnetic memory based on magnetic tunnel junctions, magnetic random access memory (MRAMs), has entered industrial production at all the major microelectronics companies. These memories combine the advantages of non-volatility (ability to keep information without being powered), writing speed (between 0.5ns and 50ns depending on the version), endurance (10^6 to 10^{15} write cycles depending on the version), low power consumption (~ 100 fJ per write), and integration density. The entry into industrial production of these memories is a very important step because it marks the adoption of this hybrid complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor (CMOS)/magnetic technology by the industry. The first industrial uses of MRAMs concern the replacement of embedded flash memories. Another major application is the replacement of static RAMs (SRAMs) used as cache memories in processors. At advanced technology nodes (sub-20nm), MRAMs are at least a factor of 4 smaller than SRAMs. Replacing SRAMs with MRAMs would increase the capacity of cache memories and thus increase the speed of processors while reducing their power consumption.

To reduce static power consumption, the concept of “normally-off/instantly-on computing” has been proposed. It consists of finely distributing MRAMs among the logic blocks so that the results of logic operations can be saved almost continuously.

Figure 3. Non-volatile magnetic memories and their position in the computing memory hierarchy (from [16]).

This makes it possible to cut the power supply to the logic blocks and memories as soon as they are temporarily not in use and to reactivate them almost instantaneously, thus reducing the power consumption associated with leakage currents. Some architectures also allow logic operations to be performed within memory blocks (logic-in memory). All this reduces data

transfers along the interconnections and thus dynamic power consumption.

Other approaches are also being studied for application in computing with much more innovative concepts:

- Magnetic materials whose properties are controlled by an electric field
- 2D spintronic materials

- Spintronic neuromorphic circuits
- Logic using electron spin directly (logic operations by spin wave manipulation. See Figure 2)
- Non-volatile logic gates combining magnetoelectric materials and spin current/charge current interconversion by spin-orbit coupling, etc.

Figure 4. Spintronic approaches for logic: non-volatile logic (top), spin-wave logic (bottom) (from [16]).

All of those very innovative approaches to computing using spintronics have the potential to lead to much more energy efficient circuits and architectures [16].

Photonics computing

Using photons for computing is not a new thing: they are already at work in high bandwidth communication links and photonics technologies have been critical in the growth of the internet. Attempts have been made to use integrated photonics technologies such as semiconductor laser diodes, photodiodes and light guides to implement fast data communication

inside a computer cabinet, between PC board or even on chips. However, photonics technology has faced major engineering issues including power, photonic/electronic conversion, and co-integration with CMOS. These have hindered its adoption in core computing functions.

Photonics computing can also benefit from the steady progress made in basic optical components: integrated lights sources such light emitting diodes (LEDs) and coherent light sources (lasers) of various wavelength and power, digital micro-mirror devices (DMD), display technologies

like liquid crystal display (LCD) or organic LED (OLED) and integrated camera technologies, high-speed photodiodes arrays and time of flight sensors (TOF). By way of example of this trend, a small company, Lighton [36], designed a photonic system for speeding up matrix-vector products [37] using laser light and off-the-shelf cameras and DMD. The optical processing unit (OPU) [38] is designed to replace power-hungry graphics processing units (GPU) and is to be integrated in data centres.

The concept of reservoir computing has also been demonstrated using photonics hardware for a dynamical system, which opens up the path to ultrafast brain-inspired computing. One implementation involves an electro-optic phase-delay dynamics designed with off-the-shelf optoelectronic telecom devices, thus providing the required wide bandwidth. The efficiency of the implementation has been demonstrated experimentally on speech-recognition tasks [39].

Quantum computing is the field in which photonics technologies are progressing the most. This is not a surprise since photons are probably the best example of quantum objects and were instrumental

Figure 5. Concept of a fully photonics analogue reservoir computer (from [17]).

Figure 6. A view on the potential roadmap for continued dimensional scaling, new transistor architectures, new materials introduction, combined with innovative interconnect architectures. (from IMEC “20-year semiconductor roadmap” [49])

in demonstrating the properties of quantum physics [40]. However, implementing photonic quantum computing gets very difficult in practical terms because of the engineering complexity of photon sources, channels, operators and detectors. Things might change thanks to recent advances in integrated photonics. The evidence of strong coupling between the electron spin in a silicon qubit and a microwave photon in a resonator [41], shows that photonics could be used to coherently couple qubits on a silicon substrate. Photonics could thus help solve the challenge of scaling-up the number of silicon-based spin qubits and open up new architecture and design opportunities. This is a further example of heterogeneous technology integration.

Silicon photonics has made tremendous progress in recent decades. Although not yet ready for general use in computing systems (for core computing tasks), it will be a key technology for the success of novel computing paradigms currently in development, in particular in high throughput machine learning tasks for artificial intelligence and in quantum computing engineering.

Progress in semiconductor technology

The mainstream evolution of digital and memory devices is very much following the roadmap and announcements on the topic that have been seen over the last few years. Look for example at the memory technol-

ogy trends exposed in [48]. Last generation FinFET at 2nm is around the corner at TSMC and, with a likely lag of about one year, at Intel. First generation gate all around (GAA, also called nanosheets or nanoribbons) are due to come in 3nm node from Samsung. Micron has started shipping their 1 α technology [47], similar to 14nm logic pitches, breaking the barrier of 0.3 Gb/mm², at 0.315 Gb/mm².

This technology trend is likely to maintain its pace for the next five years until it reaches the physical limits of the GAA structures and the fabrication technology limits related to the extreme ultraviolet (EUV) lithography and deposition tools of the current generation.

Significant activity is underway on both fronts, looking into new ways of arranging

Figure 7. in-memory computing computational RAM proof of concept: Die photograph and layout view of IMC-based C-SRAM test chip (image from [46])

Figure 8. a) E-skin (Kim et al [6]), b) Prosthetic skin with multiple sensors (Kim et al [7]) and c) E-skin pulse oximeter using OLEDs and OPDs (organic photodiodes) (Yokota et al [8])

the devices with increasing use of stacking and in developing a higher numerical aperture EUV system and other processing tools.

It seems very likely that some of these technologies will lead to a trend of about 25% improvement in density and power for the next three or four nodes. Clearly the naming of the nodes will become less and less related to the real physical dimension of the devices.

Stacking will be the trend not only at device level: it will continue to extend to assembly of multiple chips in packaging to get specialized functions closer together in order to increase speed and reduce power consumption. Before reaching true IMC, the trend demonstrated thus far by

the Intel or Apple chips will continue with increasing packaging density and a larger application of the “chiplets” concept.

Buried interconnects, monolithic 3D and “in-memory computing”

With the emergence of so-called hyper dimensional computing applications (e.g. image recognition by learning, post-quantum cryptography, etc.), that is to say, applications based on data sets that can be represented by large vectors (ranging from 128 bits to several thousand bits), current computing architectures are no longer suitable for processing them efficiently. Indeed, these applications require the processing of large amounts of data with very low computational latency to ensure an acceptable execution time. However, more than 90% of the energy of a calculation instruc-

tion can be dedicated solely to the transfer of data between the computing and the storage units.

To overcome this problem, a new concept of computing has emerged in recent years, namely in- or near-memory computing (IMC). This concept, based on the execution of relatively simple operation instructions (such as addition or multiplication of integers), uses the intrinsic properties of a certain type of memory to carry them out using much less energy than a classical computing architecture, such as the von Neumann one. This is made possible by fundamentally changing the computing paradigm by bringing the instruction and computation to the place where the data to be processed is located, rather than the other way around. For the reduction in energy and computational latency to be truly significant at the system level, the microprogramming and software compilation chain must also be optimized accordingly.

For example, an SRAM-based computing technology called computational SRAM has been proposed [42]. This technology has the advantage of being able to rely on a perfectly adapted and customizable software compilation chain developed in collaboration with the software and hardware teams. In addition, this technology is compatible with standard scalar processors (e.g. RISC-V) and other types of data memory present in the system and helps enhance computing performance and energy efficiency of computing systems.

Figure 9. Flex6502: an 8-bit 6502 CPU fabricated using PragmatIC's 0.8 μm IGZO TFTs [27]

Figure 10. NFP roadmap projection

Flexible electronics: hardware technologies for low cost and sustainable production processes

Some applications require low to extreme low-cost hardware, coupled with other requirements, such as being apt for environmentally-friendly disposal. Examples of this include smart packaging, healthcare devices and wearable electronics. The technology used for such devices is called flexible electronics, and is also known as printed electronics and thin film electronics.

Flexible electronics are thin, lightweight, flexible (as the name implies) and cheap compared to silicon-based elec-

tronics, mainly because these devices are manufactured using low-cost processes, due to lower processing temperatures and a smaller number of processing steps, and thus, masks. The materials used can be insulators, conductors and semiconductor materials, such as organic, metal oxides, amorphous silicon or 2D materials. The devices are fabricated on substrates of plastic, steel foil or paper.

Flexible electronics are applied in OLEDs, flexible displays and organic photovoltaic devices. They are increasingly finding application in smart packaging: electronics embedded into products such as fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG), or in smart blister packing for pharmaceutical products. Flexible electronics devices can be used for product tracking in logistics, for environmental tracking of products (e.g. products that must be kept at a particular temperature), and for interacting with customers using illumination and sound (and even using aromas).

In healthcare, flexible electronics are used for smart systems, and are flexible, stretchable devices attached directly to the skin. The device can be used to monitor physiological activity (electrocardiogram (ECG), electroencephalogram (EEG), electromyography (EMG)), to monitor and treat wounds [2] [3] [4], and for man-machine interfaces. These devices are fully integrated, consisting of electrodes or sensors, communications, and batteries or energy harvesters.

Computing with flexible electronics: natively flexible processors

The first natively flexible processors (NFPs) were implemented with flexible electronics with thin film transistor-based (TFT) devices [18, 19]. Although already lower in cost than silicon-based processors, the cost of these devices is still too high for FMCG applications with a shelf time of only a few days. About ten years ago, the first organic TFT-based processor was developed, using 5 μm technology [6], first in unipolar p-type technology, and soon after also in complementary technology [7][8]. This 8-bit CPU consisted of 3200 TFTs and operated at 2.1 kHz. In 2019, a RISC-V processor was manufactured using

carbon nanotube-based field-effect transistors (FETs), running at 10 kHz [9]. In 2021, a 32-bit ARM Cortex-M with memory and peripherals was produced using indium-gallium-zinc-oxide (IGZO) TFTs. This processor runs at 29 kHz and consists of 73,300 transistors [12], which is the most complex NFP built so far. And even a good old 6502, a microprocessor design dating back from the 1970's, was implemented using IGZO TFTs in 2022, running at 71 kHz and consuming 132 mW [13].

Machine learning hardware and a neural network, consisting of 4100 and 5700 TFTs and running at 104 and 22 kHz respectively, have also been recently developed [10][11].

At the moment, the technology of flexible electronics is transitioning from a phase where conventional Si-based processors are integrated with flexible electronics based peripheral devices to a phase where NFPs have sufficiently evolved to replace Si-based processors (Figure 10). Such NFPs will find application in wearables, but less so in FMCG with a very short shelf life. Wearables have longer lifetimes, and might thus require occasional software updates. Application-specific devices for consumer products can already be manufactured using flexible electronics due to their lower complexity. By the end of the decade, it is expected that the cost of NFPs will have dropped sufficiently to make them feasible for use in FMCG.

Sustainable fabrication processes

State-of-the-art chip manufacturing processes put a lot of strain on the environment, in terms of energy consumption (maintaining clean-room conditions, lithographic equipment, ovens), toxic chemicals, and use of vast quantities of clean water. One way to reduce toxic waste is to recycle some of the materials or find less toxic replacements. Semi, the semiconductor association, has launched a consortium to focus on (the challenges of) sustainable chip making [15].

Experimenting with chip processes can be very expensive, as upsetting a process too much can wreak havoc on the yield. Moreover, because of the many processing

steps required, it can take weeks before the effects can be measured.

Flexible electronics are made with processes that have far fewer steps. Results of experiments on a chip manufacturing process may take only a few days to surface. This makes the manufacturing of flexible electronics a more viable testbed for developing and testing more sustainable chip manufacturing processes [14].

In summary, although flexible electronics are not a field that will take computing to the next speed level, it is a viable technology for producing extremely cheap small processing systems with a significantly smaller environmental footprint.

Acknowledgements

- Sebastian Feld, assistant professor at Delft University of Technology
- Laurent Larger, Director, FEMTO-ST Institute, France
- Menno Lindwer, VP IP & Silicon at GrAI Matter Labs, Eindhoven
- Ioan Lucian Prejbeanu, executive director of SPINTEC research laboratory, France
- Carlo Reita, Director, Strategic Partnerships and Planning, CEA, LETI, France
- Sanaz Mahmoodi Takaghaj, assistant teaching professor, Pennsylvania State University School of Engineering Design and Innovation
- Emre Ozer, Senior Director of Processor Development, PragmatIC Semiconductor
- Yulia Sandamirskaya, research scientist at Intel Labs in Munich

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This document is part of the HIPEAC Vision available at hipeac.net/vision.

This is release v.1, January 2023.

Cite as: C. Gamrat and H. Munk. New and emerging technologies and paradigms. In M. Duranton et al., editors, *HIPEAC Vision 2023*, pages 100-109, Jan 2023.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7461887

The HIPEAC project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 871174.

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